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On a new application of almost non-increasing sequence to Ultraspherical Series associated with $(N, p, q)_k$ means

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Abstract :

In this research paper, we have introduced a brand-new application of an almost non-increasing sequence of constants to ultraspherical series associated with $(N, p, q)_k$ means. The main theorem was also used to obtain a new and widely known arbitrary result that validates the current results by using suitable conditions from previous findings. This work is motivated by the works of [3], [6], and [8].

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1. Introduction :

As a result of Cauchy's enduring work "course d'analyse algebrique" in 1821 and Abel's research (see [10]) on binomial series in 1826, the hoary, hackneyed and hazy concept of convergence of infinite series was rebutted. Nonetheless, certain non-convergent series, particularly in Dynamical Astronomy, yielded almost equivalent results in 1890, when "a theory of divergence" was proposed, which was a pioneering effort in this field.

For the first time during this period, a paper on multiplication was written by no less a personality than Cesàro (see [4], [10]). For many of the seminal and pioneering mathematical analysts of the 20th century, the theory of series, with its fluctuating partial sum sequence, was the center of their creative activity. Through relentless endeavors made by multiple eminent mathematicians that fruitful and satisfactory methods were conceived and concretized towards the far end of the last methods were devised so that certain values could be grouped together in a reasonable way as their sums in a process closely related to Cauchy's concept of convergence manner. To elaborate and elucidate further. Summability Szász and Hardy (see [8], [10]), the process of associating generalized sum, imparted a natural generalization of the classical concept of Convergence Hobson, Titchmarsh (see [10]) and is, therefore, responsible within the domain of applicability, an extensive and former rejected series which used to be forbidden as divergent. As a result, convergence has been presented as a sweeping generalization. It was only natural to explore the possibility of presenting convergence as a concept. Indeed just as the concept of convergence has resulted in the extension under the general title of summability (Kogbeltliantz (see [4]-[8])), the idea of ordinary and associate convergence have contributed to the developments of ordinary and absolute summability in the same weary. Thus, the concept of uniform convergence would have definitely underscored the concept of uniform summability highlighted prominently by analysts.

Definitions :

Ultraspherical series (see [1]) :

Let $\chi(\theta, \phi)$ be a function defined in the range $0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$ and $0 \leq \phi \leq 2\pi$. The ultraspherical series corresponding to $\chi(\theta, \phi)$ on the sphere S is given by

$$\chi(\theta, \phi) \sim \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (n + \alpha) \iint_s \frac{\lambda(\theta^1, \phi^1) Q_n^{(\alpha)}(\cos w) \sin \phi^1}{[\sin^2 \theta^1 \cdot \sin^2(\phi - \phi^1)]^{\frac{1-2\alpha}{2}}} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\cos w = \cos \theta \cdot \cos \theta^1 + \sin \theta \cdot \sin \theta^1 \cos(\phi - \phi^1). \quad (2)$$

Ultraspherical Polynomials (see[1]) :

The ultraspherical polynomials $Q_n^\alpha(x)$ is defined by the generating function

$$(1 - 2xt + t^2)^{-\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} t^n Q_n^{(\alpha)}(x), \alpha > 0 \quad (3)$$

A generalized mean value of $\chi(\theta, \phi)$ on the sphere S has been defined by Kogbetliantz (see[1])

$$f(w) = \frac{1}{2\pi(\sin w)^{2\alpha}} \int_{C_w} \frac{\chi(\theta^1, \phi^1) ds^1}{[\sin^2 \theta^1 \cdot \sin^2(\phi - \phi^1)]^{\frac{1-2\alpha}{2}}} \quad (4)$$

where the integral is taken along the small circle C where center is (θ, ϕ) on the sphere S on where curvilinear radius is w .

The series (1) reduces to

$$\chi(\theta, \phi) \sim \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha)} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (n + \alpha) \int_0^\pi f(w) \sin^2 w Q_n^\alpha(\cos w) dw. \quad (5)$$

Also we write

$$\phi(w) = [\chi(w) - B] (\sin w)^{2\pi-1} \quad (6)$$

where B is a fixed constant.

Let $\sum u_n$ be an infinite series and $\{S_n\}$ denote the sequence of its partial sums.

We consider two non-negative, monotonic increasing sequence of constant such that $p - 1 = 1$ and $q - 1 = 0$.

Also, we define P_n, Q_n and R_n in such a way that

$$P_a = \sum_{b=0}^a p_b$$

$$Q_a = \sum_{b=0}^a q_b$$

and

$$R_a = \sum_{a=0}^b q_b p_{a-b} \tag{7}$$

Definition (see [2]) :

An infinite series $\sum u_n$ or the sequence $\{S_n\}$ is said to be almost generalized Nörlund (N, p, q) summability or Nörlund (N, p, q) summable to S if

$$A_{a,b}^{p,q} = \frac{1}{R_a} \sum_{c=0}^a p_{a-c} q_c S_{c,b} \tag{8}$$

tends to $S, a \rightarrow \infty$ uniformly w.r. to m , where the sum $S_{c,b}$ is defined as follows:

$$S_{c,b} = \left(\sum_{d=b}^{c+b} S_d \right) \frac{1}{c+1} \tag{9}$$

The particular cases of the generalized Nörlund (N, p, q) mean are follows:

- (i) only for $q_\alpha = 1 \forall \alpha, A_\alpha^{p,q}$ reduces to Nörlund mean (N, p_α) .
- (ii) only for $p_\alpha = 1 \forall \alpha, A_\alpha^{p,q}$ reduces to almost Riesz method (\bar{N}, q_n) .
- (iii) only for $p_\alpha = \frac{1}{\alpha+1}$ and $q_\alpha = 1 \forall \alpha, A_\alpha^{p,q}$ reduces to $\left(N, \frac{1}{n+1}\right)$ mean and this mean is known as harmonic mean.
- (iv) only for $p_\alpha = 1$ and $q_\alpha = 1 \forall \alpha, A_\alpha^{p,q}$ reduces to the $(C, 1)$ mean.

i.e. $p_m = \binom{m+\alpha-1}{\alpha-1}$, α is a positive number, then the method (N, p_m) reduces to the method of (C, α) .

A sequence $\{S_a\}$ is said to be strongly $(N, p, q)_k, k > 0$ means

$$\text{if } \sum_{b=0}^a p_{a-b} q_b |S_a - S|^k = 0 (R_a), a \rightarrow \infty.$$

In 1924, Kogbetliantz [3] defined ordinary and absolute summability methods to deal with ultraspherical series, is known as strong summability of ultraspherical series. After his pioneer work, summability becomes a topic of interest for many mathematicians such as Gupta [4], Pandey [5], Singhai [6,7] who established many interesting results on absolute and cesàro summability of ultraspherical series. This motivates us to study the degree of approximation of a function in more generalized as particular cases. Therefore, an attempts to make an advance study, we consider the generalized (N, p, q) method of which (N, p_n) as a particular cases and to make strong $(N, p, q)_k$ summability of ultraspherical series under very general conditions in the following forms:

Theorem :

Let $\{p_a\}, \{q_a\}$ are two positive monotonically decreasing sequence of real constants with their partial sums are defined as follows:

$$P_a = \sum_{b=0}^a p_b, Q_a = \sum_{b=0}^a q_b, R_a = \sum_{b=0}^a p_{a-b} q_b,$$

where

$$P_a, Q_a, R_a \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } a \rightarrow \infty$$

and

$$\sum_{b=1}^a \left| \Delta (p_{a-b} q_b) \right| = O (R_a a^{-1}) \tag{10}$$

as $a \rightarrow \infty$.

Let η be a sufficiently large constant and $\gamma > 0$ such that

$$v < 1 - \gamma < 1, 1 > v > 0. \tag{11}$$

Let $\phi(w)$ be a function of bounded variation in the open interval (ξ, π) i.e. $|\xi(w)| \in (\xi, \pi)$, where ξ is defined as follows:

$$0 < \xi < \pi, \xi = \eta^{-\gamma} \text{ and } \xi = m^{-1}. \tag{12}$$

Let $A(z)$ and $B(z)$ are two functions of z such that $A(z)$, $B(z)$ and $z \cdot \frac{A(z)}{B(z)}$ increases with z and

$$A(m).R(m) = O \left[B \left\{ R(m) \right\} \right]. \tag{13}$$

If

$$\int_0^z |\phi(w)| d\omega = O \left[\frac{z^{\delta-1+\gamma^{-1}} \cdot A\left(\frac{1}{z}\right) u_r}{B\left\{R\left(\frac{1}{z}\right)\right\}} \right] \tag{14}$$

as $z \rightarrow 0$, where $\tau = \left(\frac{1}{z}\right)$, the integral part of $\frac{1}{z}$ and

$$\delta = \frac{2\nu + 1 - \gamma}{\gamma} \tag{15}$$

then the series (1) is summable $[N, p, q]_k, k > 0$ to the sum A .

Lemmas :

Lemma 1 (see[8]) :

If ν is a positive real number, then

$$L_a^{(\nu)}(\cos \psi) = \left\{ \psi^{-\nu} O(a^{\nu-1}) \text{ for } \frac{s}{a} \leq \psi \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \right\} \tag{16}$$

and

$$L_a^{(\nu)}(\cos \psi) = O(a^{\nu-1}), \text{ for } 0 \leq \psi \leq \frac{s}{a} \tag{17}$$

Lemma 2 (see[8]) :

If ν is a non-negative real numbers, then

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[L_a^{(\nu)}(z) \right] = 2\nu L_a^{(\nu+1)}(z) \tag{18}$$

Lemma 3 :

If $P_a \rightarrow \infty, Q_a \rightarrow \infty, R_a \rightarrow \infty$

$$\sum_{b=1}^a |\Delta(p_{a-b} q_b)| = O(R_a \cdot a^{-a}),$$

as $a \rightarrow \infty$, then

$$a^a q_a = O(R_a). \tag{19}$$

Proof : Given that

$$\sum_{b=1}^a |\Delta(p_{a-b} q_b)| = O(R_a \cdot a^{-1}),$$

where $P_a, Q_a, R_a \rightarrow \infty$ as $a \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{b=1}^a |\Delta(p_{a-b} q_b)| = O(R_a).$$

For this, we may easily obtain

$$\sum_{b=1}^1 |b \Delta(p_{a-b} q_b)| = \sum_{b=1}^a (p_{a-b} q_b) - p_a q_0 - a^a q_a p_0$$

$$\Rightarrow a^a \cdot q_a p_0 = R_a - \sum_{b=1}^{a-1} a \Delta(p_{a-b} q_b)$$

$$\Rightarrow a^a \cdot q_a = O(R_a), a \rightarrow \infty.$$

Proof of the theorem :

Let a^{th} partial sum of the series (1) be ζ . Then by Szegö theorem, we may write

$$\zeta_a = \frac{\Gamma_v}{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(\frac{1}{2} + v)} \int_0^\pi \chi(w) \sum_{d=0}^a (d+v) Q_d^{(v)}(\cos w) (\sin w)^{2v} dw$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{\Gamma_\nu}{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} + \nu\right)} \int_0^\pi \chi(w) \left[\frac{d}{dz} \left\{ Q_{a+1}^{(\nu)}(z) + Q_a^{(\nu)}(z) \right\} \right]_{z=\cos w} \times (\sin w)^{2\nu} dw \\
 \zeta_a - A &= \frac{\Gamma_\nu}{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} + \nu\right)} \int_0^\pi \phi(w) \frac{d}{dw} Q_{a+1}^{(\nu)}(\cos w) dw \\
 &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_\nu}{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} + \nu\right)} \int_0^\pi \phi(w) \frac{d}{dw} Q_a^{(\nu)}(\cos w) dw \\
 &= O \left[\int_0^\pi \phi(w) \frac{d}{dw} Q_{a+1}^{(\nu)}(\cos w) dw + O \left[\int_0^\pi \phi(w) \frac{d}{dw} Q_a^{(\nu)}(\cos w) dw \right] \right] \\
 &= O(J_1) + O(J_2) \text{ say.} \tag{20}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we have to show that

$$\sum_{b=0}^a p_{a-b} q_b |\zeta_b - B|^k = O(R_a), \quad a \rightarrow \infty. \tag{21}$$

With the help of Minkowski's inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left\{ \sum_{b=0}^a p_{a-b} q_b |\zeta_b - B|^k \right\}^{\frac{1}{k}} &\leq \left\{ \sum_{b=0}^a p_{a-b} q_b |J_1|^k \right\}^{\frac{1}{k}} + \left\{ \sum_{b=0}^a p_{a-b} q_b |J_2|^k \right\}^{\frac{1}{k}} \\
 &= K + G. \tag{22}
 \end{aligned}$$

For J_1 ,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |J_1| &= O \left[\int_0^\pi \left| \phi(w) \left| \frac{d}{dw} \left\{ Q_{a+1}^{(\nu)}(\cos w) \right\} \right| dw \right] \\
 &= O \left[\int_0^\xi \left| \phi(w) \right| 2\nu \left| \frac{d}{dw} \left\{ Q_{a+1}^{(\nu)}(\cos w) \right\} \right| dw \right] \\
 &\quad + O \left[\int_\xi^\pi \left| \phi(w) \right| 2\nu \left| \frac{d}{dw} \left\{ Q_{a+1}^{(\nu)}(\cos w) \right\} \right| dw \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= O(J_{1.1}) + O(J_{1.2}) \text{ say.} \tag{23}$$

Also for $J_{1.1}$,

$$J_{1.1} = 2\nu \int_0^\xi |\phi(w)| \left| \frac{d}{dw} \left\{ Q_{a+1}^{(\nu)}(\cos w) \right\} \right| dw$$

$$= O \left[\int_0^\xi |\phi(w)| \left| Q_{a+1}^{(\nu+1)}(\cos w) \right| dw \right] \quad \text{[by lemma (1)]}$$

$$= O \left[\left\{ (a+1)^{2\nu+1} \right\} \xi \int_0^\xi |\phi(w)| dw \right]$$

$$= O(a^{2\nu+1}) \xi \cdot O \left[\frac{\xi^{\delta-1+\gamma-1} \cdot A\left(\frac{1}{\xi}\right) \cdot q\left(\frac{1}{\xi}\right)}{B\left\{R\left(\frac{1}{\xi}\right)\right\}} \right] \quad \text{(using (14))}$$

$$= O(a^{2\nu+1}) a^{-\gamma} \cdot O \left[\frac{\xi^{\delta+\gamma-1} \cdot \frac{1}{\xi} \cdot A\left(\frac{1}{\xi}\right) \cdot q\left(\frac{1}{\xi}\right)}{B\left\{R\left(\frac{1}{\xi}\right)\right\}} \right] \quad \text{(using (12))}$$

$$= O(a^{2\nu+1}) a^{-\gamma} \cdot O \left[\frac{\xi^{\delta+\gamma-1} \cdot A(m) \cdot m \cdot q(m)}{B\left\{R(m)\right\}} \right] \quad \text{(using 12*)}$$

$$= O \left[a^{2\nu+1-\gamma} \right] \cdot O \left[\frac{\xi^{\delta+\delta-1} \cdot A(m \cdot R(m))}{B\left\{R(m)\right\}} \right] \quad \text{(using (19))}$$

$$= \left[a^{(2\nu+1-\gamma)} \right] \cdot \left(\xi^{\delta+\gamma-1} \right) \quad \text{(using (13))}$$

$$= O \left[a^{2\nu+1-\gamma-\gamma\delta-1} \right] \quad \text{(using (12))}$$

$$= O \left[a^{2\nu+1-\gamma-\gamma\left(\frac{2\nu+1-\gamma}{\gamma}\right)-1} \right] \quad \text{(using (15))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= O(a^{-1}) \\
 &= O(1), a \rightarrow \infty.
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_{1.2} &= O \left[\int_{\xi}^{\pi} \left| \phi(w) \right| \frac{d}{dw} \left\{ Q_{a+1}^{(v)}(\cos w) \right\} dw \right] \\
 &= O \left[\left\{ \left[\phi(w) Q_{a+1}^{(v)}(\cos w) \right]_{\xi}^{\pi} - \int_{\xi}^{\pi} d\phi(w) \cdot Q_{a+1}^{(v)}(\cos w) dw \right\} \right], \\
 &= O(a^{v-1}) \cdot \xi^{-v}, (\because \phi(w) \text{ is bounded variation in } (\xi, \pi)) \\
 &= O(a^{v-1+v\gamma}), \quad (\text{using (12)}) \\
 &= O(1), \text{ as } a \rightarrow \infty. \quad (\text{using (11)})
 \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

Combining (24) and (25), we have

$$J_1 = O(1), \text{ as } a \rightarrow \infty \text{ so that}$$

$$K = O(R_a), \text{ as } a \rightarrow \infty.$$

Similarity, we have to

$$G = O(R_a), \text{ as } a \rightarrow \infty.$$

Thus, we must write

$$\sum_{b=0}^a p_{a-b} q_b \left| \zeta_b - B \right|^k = O(R_a), \text{ as } a \rightarrow \infty.$$

Conclusion :

Generalization procedure is used to establish advanced systems. This process provides the extended domains of existing operations and system consistently.

Summability methods are instruct to reduce the error. Some new result can be generated by using suitable conditions in the main result. Results of Prasad [8] and Singhai [7] can be found by applying conditions on the main result.

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